

LARGE DEFLECTION ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED PLATES IN STATICS AND DYNAMICS

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ABSTRACT

A new eight node C^0 membrane-plate quadrilateral finite element is presented to analyse static and dynamic moderately large deflections of semi-thick laminates. Some numerical simulations are presented in statics and in dynamics for laminates, including buckling and transient analyses.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous research studies have been developed and are still being developed world-wide, to attempt to improve both theoretical plate models and finite elements when the transverse shear effects are significant ; as brought out in [1] for finite elements and for theoretical models , see [2]. The structural engineers need standard finite elements based on conventional engineering degrees of freedom at each node, reliability, computationally effective, simple formulation, easy to implement and its applicability to thick or thin plate situations. But structural engineering need also non standard finite elements devoted to special applications such as refined geometric models for thin shells [3] or refined structural models for composite multilayered shell [4] for instance. The present paper concerns only standard finite element tools.

The shear bending part of the present finite element has been presented in [5]. It is only recalled that the corresponding approach was based on the well known assumed strain field method for which some new criteria have been generally expressed in [5]. In our work, the membrane improvement is achieved based on the assumed strain field method. Finally, the application of this new eight node element based on the Reissner-Mindlin plate theory to laminated composite plate is investigated by considering some studies/problems for which results are available in the literature. In statics, analysis concerns the buckling and post-buckling of plates under in plane normal or shear loads whereas dynamic analysis is carried out for both nonlinear transient response and nonlinear free vibration problems.

THE MODERATELY LARGE DEFLECTION MODEL

THE TWO-DIMENSIONAL WEAK FORM

We consider a system of rectangular cartesian coordinates with respect to the fixed reference configuration at an initial time $t = 0$ so that a generic point in this system is denoted by its Lagrangian coordinates (X_1, X_2, X_3) at time t . $X_3 = Z$ is the coordinate along the normal direction to the midplane of the plate while (X_1, X_2) are the coordinates of a point along the inplane directions of the plate. The main assumptions of the Reissner-Mindlin plate theory are

now briefly mentioned. The plate domain is denoted by $\Omega(0)$ in the reference configuration and its frontier in this configuration is $\Gamma(0)$ while h is the constant thickness of the plate. So, in the reference configuration, the principle of virtual power, corresponding to two-dimensional approach, states :

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{A(0)} \left\{ \sum_{\alpha=1}^2 [I_0 \ddot{u}_\alpha u_\alpha^* + I_1 (\ddot{\omega}_\alpha u_\alpha^* + \ddot{u}_\alpha \omega_\alpha^*) + I_2 \ddot{\omega}_\alpha \omega_\alpha^*] + I_0 \ddot{w} w^* \right\} dA \\ & + \int_{A(0)} (\underline{\varepsilon}_0^{*T} \underline{N} + \underline{\varepsilon}^{*T} \underline{N} + \underline{\kappa}^{*T} \underline{M} + \underline{\gamma}^{*T} \underline{Q}) dA \\ & - \int_{A(0)} \left\{ \sum_{\alpha=1}^2 [n_\alpha u_\alpha^* + m_\alpha \omega_\alpha^*] + q w^* \right\} dA - \int_{C_f(0)} \left\{ \sum_{\alpha=1}^2 [N_\alpha u_\alpha^* + M_\alpha \omega_\alpha^*] + P w^* \right\} dS = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $A(0)$ is the area of the middle plane of the plate, $C_f(0)$ the edge of the middle plane of the plate, and u_α^* , ω_α^* , w^* virtual motions associated to membrane motions u_α , rotations ω_α of the fibre initially normal to the middle plane of the plate, and w the deflection. In addition, we have defined inertial terms (ρ_0 the mass density) by :

$$\ddot{v} = \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} ; I_\beta = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \rho_0 Z^\beta dZ, \beta = 0, 1, 2 \quad (2)$$

and the generalized virtual strain rates are :

$$\underline{\varepsilon}_0^{*T} = \left\{ \frac{\partial u_1^*}{\partial X_1} \quad \frac{\partial u_2^*}{\partial X_2} \quad \frac{\partial u_1^*}{\partial X_2} + \frac{\partial u_2^*}{\partial X_1} \right\} ; \underline{\kappa}^{*T} = \left\{ \frac{\partial \omega_1^*}{\partial X_1} \quad \frac{\partial \omega_2^*}{\partial X_2} \quad \frac{\partial \omega_1^*}{\partial X_2} + \frac{\partial \omega_2^*}{\partial X_1} \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$\underline{\varepsilon}^{*T} = \left\{ \frac{\partial w}{\partial X_1} \quad \frac{\partial w^*}{\partial X_1} \quad \frac{\partial w}{\partial X_2} \quad \frac{\partial w^*}{\partial X_2} \quad \frac{\partial w}{\partial X_1} \quad \frac{\partial w^*}{\partial X_2} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial X_2} \quad \frac{\partial w^*}{\partial X_1} \right\} ; \underline{\gamma}^{*T} = \left\{ \omega_1^* + \frac{\partial w^*}{\partial X_1} \quad \omega_2^* + \frac{\partial w^*}{\partial X_2} \right\}$$

Also, generalized stresses are :

$$\underline{N}^T = \{ N_{11} \quad N_{22} \quad N_{12} \} ; \underline{M}^T = \{ M_{11} \quad M_{22} \quad M_{12} \} ; \underline{Q}^T = \{ Q_{13} \quad Q_{23} \} \quad (4)$$

while prescribed loads are given by :

$$n_\alpha = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} f_\alpha dZ ; m_\alpha = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} Z f_\alpha dZ ; q = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} f_3 dZ ; N_\alpha = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} F_\alpha dZ ; M_\alpha = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} Z F_\alpha dZ ; P = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} F_3 dZ \quad (5)$$

GENERALIZED CONSTITUTIVE LAW FOR MODERATELY LARGE DEFLECTIONS

The global constitutive law is of the following form which takes into account for moderately large deflections :

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{N} &= \underline{A} \underline{\varepsilon}_0 + \underline{B} \underline{\kappa} + \underline{A} \underline{\varepsilon} \\ \underline{M} &= \underline{B} \underline{\varepsilon}_0 + \underline{D} \underline{\kappa} + \underline{B} \underline{\varepsilon} \\ \underline{Q} &= \underline{E} \underline{\gamma} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where (\underline{C} ' is the classical local elastic constitutive law for angle ply laminates taking into account of the assumption $S_{33} = 0$)

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{A} &= \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} \underline{C}_p dZ, \quad \underline{B} = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} Z \underline{C}'_p dZ, \quad \underline{D} = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} Z^2 \underline{C}_p dZ, \quad \underline{E} = \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} \underline{C}_s dZ \\ \underline{\epsilon}_0^T &= \left\{ \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial X_1}, \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial X_2}, \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial X_2} + \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial X_1} \right\}, \quad \underline{\kappa}^T = \left\{ \frac{\partial \omega_1}{\partial X_1}, \frac{\partial \omega_2}{\partial X_2}, \frac{\partial \omega_1}{\partial X_2} + \frac{\partial \omega_2}{\partial X_1} \right\} \\ \underline{\gamma}^T &= \left\{ \omega_1 + \frac{\partial w}{\partial X_1}, \omega_2 + \frac{\partial w}{\partial X_2} \right\}, \quad \underline{e}^T = \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial X_1} \right)^2, \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial X_2} \right)^2, \frac{\partial w}{\partial X_1} \frac{\partial w}{\partial X_2} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

In matrix \underline{C}' , shear correction factors are taken equal to 5/6.

CONSISTENT LINEARISATION OF THE WEAK FORM

For a Newton-type method, knowledge of the tangent stiffness of the plate is required. It can be obtained using standard linearisation procedures as given in [6], by Taylor expansion of the weak form. So, the linearised form for the principle of virtual power may be written as :

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{A(0)} \left\{ \underline{\epsilon}_0^{*T} (\underline{A} \Delta \underline{\epsilon}_0 + \underline{B} \Delta \underline{\kappa} + \underline{A} \Delta \underline{e}) + \underline{e}^{*T} (\underline{A} \Delta \underline{\epsilon}_0 + \underline{B} \Delta \underline{\kappa} + \underline{A} \Delta \underline{e}) \right. \\ \left. + \underline{\kappa}^{*T} (\underline{B} \Delta \underline{\epsilon}_0 + \underline{D} \Delta \underline{\kappa} + \underline{B} \Delta \underline{e}) + \underline{\gamma}^{*T} \underline{E} \Delta \underline{\gamma} + \Delta \underline{e}^{*T} \underline{N} \right\} dA \\ = -\mathcal{P}_a^* (\bar{\underline{U}}, \bar{\underline{U}}^*) + \mathcal{P}_e^* (\bar{\underline{U}}^*) + \mathcal{P}_1^* (\bar{\underline{U}}, \bar{\underline{U}}^*) \quad \text{for all } \bar{\underline{U}}^* \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The left side of Eqn (8) is the incremental part and is the tangent operator. Hence, the linearisation of the constitutive law given by Eqn (6) is immediate.

MEMBRANE-SHEAR-BENDING FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

To achieve numerical results from the boundary value problem stated at the preceding section; we use a finite element approximation of Eqn (8).

We note $\bar{\underline{U}}^h$ and $\bar{\underline{V}}^{*h}$ as the approximated fields of $\bar{\underline{U}}$ and $\bar{\underline{V}}^*$, respectively. The superscript h refers to the association of spaces containing $\bar{\underline{U}}^h$ and $\bar{\underline{V}}^{*h}$ with a mesh $U_{A_e^h(0)}$ (or discretisation) of the midplane domain $A(0)$ which is parametrised by a characteristic length scale h .

The finite element developed in this paper is based on the assumed strain field method for membrane and transverse shear. So, here from the classical isoparametric interpolation for the eight node membrane part of the quadrilateral element, strains are transformed into their values in natural coordinates. Then, in these last coordinates, strains are computed at some points consistently chosen by taking into account of final degree of interpolations. They are completely defined after each derivative in strain definitions which have the same monomial terms in respect to natural coordinates. Such an operation requires using a consistent polynomial truncation procedure, which is fully defined by our criteria presented in [5]. This new interpolation being characterised from well chosen points (but not from the nodes of the element), strains are returned into the physical coordinates and so, all other necessary computations are completely standard, following the classical isoparametric approach. The finite element approximation of the linearized form of Eqn (8) is then given by :

$$\underline{M} \bar{\underline{q}} + \underline{K}_T (\bar{\underline{q}}) \Delta \underline{q} = \underline{g} - \underline{h} \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{q} is the vector of degrees of freedom and $\bar{\mathbf{q}}$ its known value in the linearisation procedure. In Eqn (9), $\mathbf{K}_T(\bar{\mathbf{q}})$ is the tangent stiffness matrix, \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix and \mathbf{g} the vector of external loads, while \mathbf{h} is the vector of internal load.

The nonlinear Eqn (9) obtained are solved by Newmark numerical integration method. Equilibrium is achieved for each time step (load step in case of static) through modified Newton-Raphson iteration scheme until the results converge within the specific tolerance limit of less than 1%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Basic tests, necessary to validate a membrane-shear-bending finite element, have been passed by the eight node quadrilateral developed here. The aim of the present investigation is to see the efficacy of the formulation of the new element for the linear/nonlinear analysis of laminated composite plates in statics, buckling and vibrations. As such, problems for which solutions are available in literature are considered here. Since the finite element is derived based on consistency approach, exact integration is used to evaluate all the stiffness matrices. Unless specified otherwise, one quarter of the plate with 4x4 mesh is used for the dynamic case.

Nonlinear free vibration/postbuckling analysis is solved using eigenvalue formulation whereas transient vibration studies are carried out by employing direct integration method. To solve the nonlinear eigenvalue problems, an iterative procedure is used. The iteration starts from a corresponding initial mode shape obtained from linear analysis, with amplitude scaled up by a factor. Based on this initial mode shape, the nonlinear stiffness matrix is formed and an eigenvalue and its corresponding vector are obtained. This eigenvector is then scaled up again and the iteration continues until the required convergence criteria is achieved. For the transient response studies, all the initial conditions are assumed to be zero, and the forces to be suddenly applied uniform loads retained on the structure indefinitely. Since the solution for available examples, in general, is based on Newmark integration scheme, the present formulation is tested with the same integration scheme for transient analysis. The value of α and β (controlling parameters for stability and accuracy of the solution) in the Newmark's integration are taken as 0.5 and 0.25 which corresponds to the unconditionally stable scheme in linear analysis.

LINEAR BUCKLING ANALYSIS

For a single layer (different thickness ratio) and three ply orthotropic (different modular ratio) cases of simply supported plate under uniaxial normal stress, the material and geometric properties as given in [7] are used. The buckling parameter λ^* obtained here is given in Table 1 along with those of Srinivas and Rao [7]. The present results are fairly in good agreement with the three-dimensional elasticity solution.

Table 1. Buckling parameter of simply supported single layer orthotropic (C=1) and three-ply orthotropic laminate (h/b=0.1) under applied load N_{11} , as in [7] $\lambda^* = 12N_{11}b^2 / \pi^2 A_{11}h^2$

Single layer orthotropic plate (C = 1)			Three-ply orthotropic laminate (h/b = 0.1)		
h/b	λ^*	Ref. [7]	C	λ^*	Ref. [7]
0.05	2.9747	2.9660	1	2.7970	2.770
0.1	2.7970	2.770	2	3.4156	3.330
0.2	2.2734	2.2100	3	4.4046	4.046

NONLINEAR STATIC ANALYSIS

Numerical study is conducted for the problem for which experimental results are available [8]. In Figure 1, centre deflection versus the load parameter is presented for simply supported orthotropic square plate ($a=b=12$ in., $h=0.138$ in.) under uniform load. The material properties used are :

$$E_L = 3 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}, \quad E_T = 1.28 \times 10_{LT}^6 \text{ psi}, \quad G_{LT} = G_{TT} = 0.37 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}, \quad \nu_{LT} = 0.32$$

NONLINEAR DYNAMIC ANALYSIS

The capability of the present element is now validated by nonlinear free vibration of laminated composite square plates with simply supported boundary conditions. Table 2 gives the frequency ratio versus amplitude-to-thickness ratio for a single layer orthotropic and cross-ply laminated plates, along with the results of [9]. Next, nonlinear transient dynamic for cross-ply plate under uniform load is carried out. The variation of centre deflection with time for two values of side-to-thickness ratio ($a/h = 5, 10$) is shown in Figure 2. The results reveal that they agree very well with the available finite element solution in [9] and [10].

Table 2. Frequency ratio ω_{NL} / ω_L of nonlinear free vibrations of simply supported single layer orthotropic and $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ cross-ply laminated square plates ($a/h = 100$).

w/h	Single layer orthotropic plate	Three layers cross-ply laminate ($0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$)	
	ω_{NL}/ω_L (present)	ω_{NL}/ω_L (present)	ω_{NL}/ω_L Ref [9]
0.2	1.04152	1.0413	1.0411
0.4	1.1606	1.1577	1.1503
0.6	1.3448	1.3324	1.3165
0.8	1.5823	1.5307	1.5140
1.0	2.1473	1.9643	

CONCLUSION

The capabilities and accuracy of the formulation of the present new element for static and dynamic analysis of laminated composite plates have been demonstrated here by considering some problems on linear and nonlinear responses. The present element is shown to give very good results for laminated plates involving moderately large deflections and small rotations.

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Figure 1 Experimental correlation of the present results (centre deflection) with that of Zaghoul (simply-supported, orthotropic square plate under uniformly distributed load).

Figure 2 The effect of plate thickness on the transient response of the two-layered ($0^\circ/90^\circ$) cross-ply laminated square plates ($q=0.005 \text{ N/m}^2$, $\Delta t=0.1 \text{ s}$)

